

EARTH SCIENCES

ACTINIDES Th AND U IN THE ATMOSPHERE OF A CITY IN THE CRYOLITHOZONE

Vladimir Makarov

Doctor of Philosophy

Institute of Permafrost, Yakutsk, Russia

Abstract

Th and U levels in particulate matter (PM) in the near-ground atmosphere of Yakutsk were studied. During 2019-2020, the chemical composition of PM in summer atmosphere, as well as in the solid and soluble phases of snowpack were investigated. Concentrations of Th and U were found to decrease in the soil-PM dust-PM snow system, but the U level is an order of magnitude higher than that of Th in the aqueous phase of snow. Amphiboles, as well as pyroxenes for Th and carbonates for U are specific minerals for PM that correlate with the actinides. The daily deposition of actinides from the atmosphere in the city is estimated at Th - 46 and U - 16 mg/m² PM particles with a high content of Th and U.

Keywords: city, atmosphere, particulate matter, dispersion, minerals, actinides, thorium, uranium, toxicity

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) is the generic term referring to solid particles and aerosols that are directly emitted into the air, as well as secondary particles formed in the atmosphere from gaseous precursors. The exposure of humans to high concentrations of airborne PM can have a detrimental effect on health [3]. Airborne particles vary in chemical composition, as well as in size which can range from 0.01 micrometers (µm) to 100 µm.

The level of particulate pollution is an important indicator of the quality of the air people breathe. The harmful effect of PM is linked to its resorptive action and thus it is placed in the 3rd health hazard category.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A geochemical study of particulate matter in the urban atmosphere of Yakutsk was performed both for summer and winter seasons. To measure summertime PM, 10 dust gauges were installed across the city. Dust samples were collected from July 17 to October 15, 2019. Data from air chemistry monitoring conducted year round at the Tuymaada site of the Melnikov Permafrost Institute were also used. To obtain information on wintertime atmospheric PM, 80 snow samples were collected in March 2020 from various parts of the city. Wintertime PM level and chemical composition were determined by analyzing both the soluble and solid phases of snowpack.

Samples were analyzed at the Laboratory of Permafrost Groundwater and Geochemistry, Melnikov Permafrost Institute (analysts L.Y. Boitsova, E.S. Petrova and O.V. Shepeleva) and the Analytical Certified Test Centre, Institute of Microelectronics Technology and High-Purity Materials (Chernogolovka). Concentrations of Th and U were determined using mass spectrometry (X-7, Thermo Elemental, USA).

All analyses on snow samples were performed using approved methods and standard reference materials at the certified laboratories and followed the internal and external quality control procedures.

DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The city of Yakutsk is situated within the Tuymaada Valley in the middle Lena River, extending for 20 km on its left bank. It is the oldest city in the zone of continuous permafrost and the third largest city in the Far Eastern Federal District after Vladivostok and Khabarovsk. Its population has been rapidly increasing in recent years, from 195,000 in 2000 to 323,000 in 2020.

Yakutsk has a radial concentric city plan. The dense net of streets forms a large number of small blocks 2 to 8 ha in area. The roadways are generally elevated on embankments. The character of development varies from predominantly one or two-story buildings in the outskirts to high-rise concrete buildings, 4-5 to 9-16 stories in height.

According to the Grigoryev and Budyko climate classification system [4], Yakutsk lies within the dry climatic zone (aridity index of 1.0 to 2.0) with warm summers and cold, low-snow winters. The main seasons are dominated by continental air masses of temperate latitudes and by Arctic air masses. Prevailing winds in the city area are, thus, from the north and northwest. A characteristic feature of the wind regime is the high frequency of calms, especially in December to February, with average wind speeds of 0.8 m/s, while the mean annual wind speed is 2.4 m/s. Mean annual air temperature varied over the period of continuous instrumented observations (1883-2020) between -7.2 and -12.1°C. Mean annual precipitation is 235 mm.

Permafrost in the city area varies in thickness from 250 to 450 m, while the active layer thickness is in the range of 1.5 to 2.0 m.

There are about 160 large enterprises in Yakutsk which have stationary sources emitting 11,700 tons of pollutants annually [2]. These mainly include power stations and numerous boilers fueled by natural gas, as well as construction industry. The number of motor vehicles registered by the Yakutsk Road Traffic Safety Inspectorate is about 119,000 (as of 2018). Vehicles emit about 34,000 tons of pollutants. The level of air pollution in Yakutsk is estimated as moderately high.

The geology of the area is determined by its location at the boundary between two major units of the Siberian Platform: the Aldan High and the Vilyuy Basin.

In geochemical aspect, the area lies within the Vilyuy lithosiderophile province with V, Ti, Mn, P, Sb, Sn, Li, Nb, and U concentrations close to the crustal average and the Lena-Aldan chalcophile zone with accumula-

tions of Se, Pb, Ag, Bi, and Au. The geochemical composition of the hypergenesis zone which can provide a source of elements to the atmosphere is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Components of the hypergenesis zone	Concentration coefficient (relative to crustal abundance [1])					n
	0.7-1.0	1.0-1.5	1.5-2.0	>2.0	>5.0	
Alluvium, Q	P, V, Cr, Ni, Mn, Y Zn, Cu, Ca, Ge, Nb, La, Yb, Sc, Ti, U, Th	Li, Be, Sn, B Mo, Au	Ag, Pb, W	Co	-	124
Urban soils	Li, P, V, Cr, Ni, Y Cu, Ca, Ge, Nb, Sn, La	Ti, Mn, Zn, Y, Mo, Tl, U, Th	W	B, Ag, Pb, Co	Hg	1769

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Anthropogenic geochemical anomalies of heavy metals, rare elements and radioactive elements have been detected in the near-surface atmosphere of Yakutsk. Uranium concentrations slightly above natural

background levels form expansive halos in the downtown area, while thorium forms localized point anomalies (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Actinide concentrations in the soluble phase of snowpack, $\mu\text{g/l}$.

Analysis of the samples collected by dust gauges has shown that PM in the near-surface summertime atmosphere is a mixture of solid particles of different sizes. In all samples, PM₁₀₋₁₀₀ (particles with the diameter between 10 and 100 μm , i.e., dust) comprise about 70% of the total PM. Th and U are mostly contained in PM₁₀₋₁₀₀ together with siderophile elements, such as Ti, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Ga, Sr, Zr, Sn, La and W which are supplied to the atmosphere mainly with iron group minerals. The actinide levels decrease in both coarser and finer PM, although not synchronously.

The mineralogical composition of the bulk of summertime particulate matter (PM₁₀₋₁₀₀) in the urban air is represented by quartz (36%), carbonates (36%) and feldspar (24%) in the light fraction and by amphiboles (49%), epidote and pyroxenes (10-11%), and ilmenite and garnets (about 7%) in the heavy fraction. Finer wintertime particulate matter (PM₁₀) is composed mainly of carbonates (about 70%), carbonaceous compounds (15%), inclusions of quartz and feldspar (10%) and ferruginous plant detritus (5%). Specific mineral phases correlating with actinides deposited on the soil surface

in the zone of anthropogenic impact are pyroxenes and amphiboles for Th, and carbonates and amphiboles for U.

Average actinide levels in atmospheric and lithospheric components in the Yakutsk area are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Average actinide levels in environmental components, mg/kg.

Environmental component	Th	U	Reference
Atmosphere			
Wintertime aerosols (snow)	$0.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Author
Wintertime PM (snow)	1.45	0.52	
Summertime PM	5.5	1.54	
Lithosphere			
Lithosphere	13.0	2.5	[1]
Sands, sandstones	6.7	2.0	[3]
Soils, Central Yakutia	7.3	1.72	[7]
Soils, Tuymaada Yakutia	10.6	2.4	

The Th and U concentrations uniformly decrease in the system: soils – summertime PM – wintertime PM – aerosols and gases. Th dominates in the soils, as well as in summer and winter PM, while the level of U in the aqueous phase of snow is an order of magnitude higher than that of Th.

The value of the aerosol accumulation coefficient indicates that during the formation of aerosols, the concentration of actinides in PM decreases by one mathematical order in comparison with the alluvial soils of Central Yakutia. Both U and Th are elements with a negative intensity of aerosol enrichment. The lower Th and U levels in continental aerosols of the area are due to the composition of source material, mainly polymictic sands, released to the troposphere as aerosol particles.

About 90% of actinides is deposited during the warm season. Summertime deposition rates are on average $0.233 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$ for Th and $0.084 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$ for U (Th/U=2.8) with maximum values of 0.934 and $0.274 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$, respectively.

Wintertime solid deposition (predominantly PM_{10}) accounts for about 10% of the total atmospheric deposition of actinides in Yakutsk. The wintertime deposition rate is one order of magnitude lower for Th ($0.028 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$) and two orders of magnitude lower for U ($0.008 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$) compared to summertime deposition (Th/U=3.5).

Minimum amounts of actinides are deposited through wintertime deposition with aerosols and gases (the soluble phase of snow) with average rates of $\text{Th}=0.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$ and $\text{U}=8 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{day}$ (Table 3) at Th/U=0.11.

Table 3

Daily rates of actinide deposition from the atmosphere.

Actinide	Statistical parameter	Summer PM		Winter snow				Total deposition mg / m ² year
		mg / m ² day	%	Dust		Aerosols		
				mg / m ² day	%	mg / m ² day	%	
Th	C_{avg}	0.233	89	0.028	11	$0.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$n \cdot 10^{-7}$	46.5
	C_{max}	0.934	95	0.053	5	$0.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$n \cdot 10^{-6}$	169
U	C_{avg}	0.084	91	0.008	9	$0.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$n \cdot 10^{-6}$	16.4
	C_{max}	0.274	97	0.009	3	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$n \cdot 10^{-5}$	48

Note: C_{max} – maximum concentration, C_{avg} – average concentration.

The total atmospheric deposition of actinides in Yakutsk is estimated to be about $63 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{year}$, two third of which is Th. At sites of strong anomalies, this value can be three times higher, reaching $217 \text{ mg/m}^2 \cdot \text{year}$, the majority also consisting of Th.

The total deposition of actinides comprises $n \cdot 10^{-3}$ % of the total atmospheric deposition of pollutants.

The majority of actinide input into the active-layer soils is from the atmosphere. As most of Th and U is

deposited with the dust fraction of PM their mobility is largely limited to the soil surface. However, the presence of Th and U in the soluble phase of snowpack allows them to penetrate deep into the active layer with meltwater and concentrate in soil water. There is a correlation of actinide levels in snowpack and suprapermfrost water (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Actinide concentrations in suprapermfrost water and snowpack.

The mobility of U in the active layer and suprapermfrost water is enhanced by increased alkalinity values (pH=7.2-7.7) and certain openness of the soils with redox potential averaging 419 mV.

SUMMARY

A geochemical study of particulate matter in the urban atmosphere of Yakutsk was performed both for summer and winter (soluble and solid phases of snowpack) seasons. The study indicates the formation of anthropogenic anomalies of heavy metals, rare elements and radioactive elements in the near-surface atmosphere. The actinides of interest form extensive weak anomalies in the downtown (U) and localized point anomalies across the city (Th).

Summertime PM consist of solid particles of different sizes. Th and U are mostly contained in the dust fraction (PM₁₀₋₁₀₀) together with siderophile elements. Wintertime PM consists of finer particles, mostly PM₁₀.

Specific mineral phases correlating with actinides deposited on the soil surface in the zone of anthropogenic impact are pyroxenes and amphiboles for Th, and carbonates and amphiboles for U.

The Th and U concentrations uniformly decrease in the system: soils – summertime PM – wintertime PM (snow) – aerosols and gases (snow). Th dominates in the soils, as well as in summer and winter PM, while the level of U in the aerosol and gas component is an order of magnitude higher than that of Th due to higher mobility.

The majority of actinides (about 90%) is deposited during the summer season. Wintertime solid deposition accounts for about 10% of the total atmospheric deposition of actinides. Wintertime deposition of Th and U with aerosols and gases is minimal.

The total deposition of actinides in Yakutsk is estimated to be about 63 mg/m²·year, two third of which is Th. At sites of strong anomalies, this value can exceed 200 mg/m²·year, the majority also consisting of Th.

The sources of actinides into the near-surface atmosphere of Yakutsk are mainly fugitive dust, vehicle emissions, and to a lesser extent, emissions from power generating facilities.

The deposition of Th and U in mobile forms (in the soluble phase of snowpack) allows them to penetrate deep into the active layer with meltwater and concentrate in soil water.

Based on the snow contamination index, wintertime air pollution is estimated to be low over most of the city and moderate in areas of high traffic and near the power facilities.

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